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THE COUNCIL OF TIBET ACCORDING TO THE *sBa bzhed*

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The most important historical text dealing with the reign of King Khri srong lde btsan is without doubt the *sBa bzhed*. It was already acknowledged in the 1930's by Vostrikov in his famous work *Tibetan Historical Literature*, even though the text was not accessible to him:

“As regards the works, which the Tibetan tradition – oral and written – usually ascribes to this earliest period of Tibetan history, apparently there is only one such work, and that too absolutely conjectural. This is the so-called *Annals of the bSam-yas Monastery* (*bSam-yas-lo-rgyus*) or *Great record of the bSam-yas Monastery* (*bSam-yas-dkar-chag-chen-mo*) which contains a general account of the history of Tibet and is, therefore, known in Tibetan historical literature under the name of *The Royal Genealogy, Compiled by (the Minister from) Ba* (*rGyal-rabs sBa-bzhed*), or simply *The Work of (Minister from) Ba* (*sBa-bzhed*).

“This work is ascribed to the Minister of the King Khri-srong-lde'u-btsan (8th century), the well-known sBa gsal-snang, sBa Sang-shi, and others and enjoys great fame and authority in Tibetan historiography. It has been referred to in the works of Sa-skya-paṇḍita Kun-dga'-rgyal-mtshan (1182–1251), Bu-ston Rin-chen-grub (1290–1364), 'Gos-lo-tsa-ba gZhon-nu-dpal (1392–1481), the Fifth Dalai Lama Ngag-dbang-bLo-bzang-rgya-mtsho (1617–1682) and his regent, the well-known scholar sDe-srid Sangs-rgyas-rgya-mtsho (1653–1705), Sum-pa Ye-shes-dpal-'byor, and other authors. And, in fact, the chronology of the ancient history of Tibet as adopted in *sBa-bzhed* has, according to Sum-pa-mkhan-po, served as the basis (*rtsa-ba*) for the chronology of Bu-ston Rin-chen-sgrub and for a number of other historians as, for instance, dPa'-bo gTsug-lag-phreng-ba (1504–1566), 'Brug-pa Padma-dkar-po (b. 1527), Mang-thos-klu-

sgrub (b. 1523), for the author of the historical work *rGyal-rab-gsal-ba'i-me-long* (15th century), for the author of *Deb-ther-dmar-po* (14th century) etc.

“Unfortunately, this work *sBa-bzhed* is not at our disposal. Even in the last century, the Tibetan writers considered it a bibliographical rarity. We are, therefore, not in a position to judge specifically about its contents or about the actual date of its composition. According to Sum-pa-mkhan-po, this work was written by sBa gSal-snang, sBa Sang-shi and others as the chronicle of the bSam-yas monastery and was later subjected to various interpolations and abridgements by monks, kings and ministers. This gave rise to three versions of the text: *bLa-bzhed*, i.e. “The Work of the Monks”; *rGyal-bzhed*, i.e. “The Work of the Kings”; and *sBa-bzhed*, i.e. “The Work of (the Minister from) sBa”. Thus, we cannot normally expect ever to find the actual original text of this work. But we cannot, of course, assert that it will not turn out to be dating from a period earlier than that ascribed by the Tibetan tradition.”¹

Since this was written, two different versions of the *sBa bzhed* have surfaced, and we find it quoted in many historical texts as already mentioned by Vostrikov. The first edition of the *sBa bzhed* to be accessible to Tibetological research was R. A. Stein’s edition from 1961, *Une Chronique ancienne de bSam yas: sBa bžed* (forthwith: *BZS*), and this has until recently continued to be our only text by the name of *sBa bzhed*. But in 1980 another text was published in China under the title *sBa bzhed ces bya ba las sBa gsal snang gi bzhed pa bzhugs* (*BZC*). In the following I will study these two basic text editions of the *sBa bzhed*, but only with regard to The Council of Tibet. In addition to these two texts I will refer to three general histories: The *Chos 'byung mkhas pa'i dga' ston* (*CBKhG*) completed by dPa' bo gtsug lag 'phreng ba in 1565, the *Bu ston Chos 'byung* (*BCB*) from 1322, and finally the *rNying ma'i chos 'byung chen mo* (*NRCB*) written by Nyang ral pa chen (1136–1204).

The history of The Council of Tibet has already been treated by several scholars; the two standard works being Demiéville’s *Le Concile de Lhasa* from 1952 and Tucci’s *Minor Buddhist texts, Part II: First Bhāva-*

¹ Vostrikov (1970) pp. 24–26. I am here quoting Vostrikov without his bibliographical notes.

nākrāma of Kamalaśīla from 1958. But neither of these use the material found in the *sBa bzhed*: only in the 1970’s is this material used in research dealing with The Council of Tibet.² Since then several scholars have used the *BCB* and the *CBKhG* as sources, but always with great caution, as it has been unknown how much the authors of these texts have changed or edited their sources. Especially Japanese scholars have done extensive research on parts of the *sBa bzhed*, and have identified several of the persons mentioned in the text.³

But with the publication of Houston’s *Sources for a History of the bSam yas Debate* we find for the first time an attempt to deal with some of the available historical sources. Unfortunately Houston’s work does not compare or in any other way treat the sources; his work is solely an annotated transcription and translation of the texts.⁴ What therefore is needed is a critical comparison between the different sources to try to determine their textual filiation and interdependence.

BZS

The edition of the *sBa bzhed* published by R. A. Stein is known under the name of *sBa bzhed zhabs brtags ma* (the *sBa bzhed* with an Addendum). The main text of the *sBa bzhed* begins with the reign of Khri lde gtsug btsan (c. 704–55) and ends with the reign of Khri srong lde btsan (c. 797); the addendum continues from there with the ascendance to the throne of Mu ne btsan po and ends with Atiśa going to Central Tibet.

The Colophon p. 92, 1–9 says:

² I will not attempt a bibliography, since this has already been done, but refer the reader to the following works containing good bibliographies: Demiéville (1979) and Mala et Kimura (1981). Recently two important works containing articles dealing with the Council of Tibet have been published: *Early Ch’an in China and Tibet*. (Eds.) L. Lancaster and W. Lai, Berkeley Buddhist Series 5, Berkeley 1983, and *Studies in Ch’an and Hua-yen*. (Eds.) R. M. Gimello and P. N. Gregory, Studies in East Asian Buddhism No. 1, Honolulu 1983.

See also Mala (1985) and Faber (1985).

³ See Yampolsky (1983) pp. 7–8 and the bibliographical references in Demiéville (1979) and Mala et Kimura (1981).

⁴ See also the review of Houston’s work by P. Kværne in *Acta Orientalia* Vol. 43 (1982), pp. 141–2, and especially L. W. J. van der Kuijp: *Miscellanea to a recent contribution on/to the bSam-yas Debate*. *Kailash* 11, 3–4 (1984), pp. 149–84.

sBa bzhed rgyas par grags mchan dkyus su bris par 'dug pas/ yi ge mang ba tsam du 'dug go sba bzhed 'di la zhabs btags ma zhes pa 'di yin/ sBa bzhed rang gi ngo bo bka' tshid (sic!) kyi yi ge ni gsum du mchis tel/ gcig bse'i sgrom bur stsal nas ka la lcags kyi btab nas rje'i phyag sbal na mchis te gnod sbyin dam rgya nag po la gtad dol/ che long gcig ni zhang blon rnams la yang dar bar byas so/ ces pa yan yin 'dug 'di rnams yi ge rnying pa la mchan bu dkyus su bcugs sogs/ bris nor mang rab 'ong gi 'dug na'ang/ 'di gnyis gsum dang btug pas don la ma dag pa mi'dug go/ 'di bu tshal pho rang ba:i dpe 'khyar pa gcig dang/ gzhan gcig dang gsum bstun pas 'di kho na dag par 'dug go sba rnams kyi rjes 'brel phal cher gsang sngags blor mi bshong bas padma 'byung gnas la mi gus zer ba ni mi bden pa 'dra'o// //

“Since the (text) known as *The extensive sBa bzhed* is written with lengthy notes, it is quite wordy. The present *sBa bzhed* is the one called the (*sBa bzched with an*) *Addendum*. The basic *sBa bzched* continues until (the end of the sentence) ‘Three copies of the edict were made. One was put in a leather box and the lid was locked, and then put in the royal archives; (another) was entrusted to the *yakṣa* Dam rgya nag po. One copy was also spread among the *zhang blon*.’

“To these old texts were added long notes. Although a large number of errors were made in the writing, I compared two or three (versions) to clarify the meaning. This version is in accordance with the faulty edition from the Bu tshal pho rang ba family as well as another one; therefore this present edition is the only correct one.

“It is commonly said that because the *sBa* family and their adherents do not believe the secret tantras, they are not devoted to Padma Sambhava; but this does not seem true.”

In the colophon it is stated that the main text ends with the sentence: *bka' tshid (sic!) kyi yi ge ni gsum du mchis tel/... ..che long gcig ni zhang blon rnams la yang dar bar byas so/*. We find this passage *bka' tshig kyi yi ge zhib mo ni gsum du mchis tel/... ..che long gcig zhang blon rnams la yang dag (sic!) par byas/* on p. 62, 13. But the author of the colophon is clearly mistaken; this passage relates to the king's edict after the discussion between Kamalaśīla and *hva shang* Mahāyāna. First on p. 65, 13 do we find the actual end of the main text, which is similar to the other passage:

(btsan po'i) bka'i tshigs kyi yi ge zhib mo gsum las/ gcig lha sa na yod/ gcig khams su khyer/ gcig rje'i phyag sbal na mchis so/

“Of the three accurate copies of the King's edict, one is in Lhasa, one was brought to Khams, and one is in the royal archives.”

This passage relates to the copies of the *sBa bzched* itself and is the end sentence of the main edition; this is also clearly supported by the orthography of the text itself, which continues with a new paragraph, beginning thus:

sras mu ne btsan po dgung lo bco lnga lon tsa na jo mo ru yong bza' 'di man la zhabs brtags mar byed pa yin/

The last sentence “here below is the addendum made” is written as a note in the usual way with smaller letters.

That the writer of the colophon of *BZS* is mistaken is also supported by *BZC*, which has no addendum and ends on p. 82, 9:

btsan po mnga' bdag gi bka' gtsigs kyi yi ge zhib mo gsum las/ gcig lha sa na yod/ gcig khams su khyer/ gcig rje'i phyag na bzhugs so/

As mentioned by Vostrikov the text has been edited and revised several times after its composition, and we do not have an original edition today. The task of determining the original material from the later additions is a very difficult but a highly important task. This is only possible by comparing the text with other old histories which quote the *sBa bzched*.

Already Tāranātha (b. 1575) mentions the problem of later editions in his Padma Sambhava biography:

des na rgyal po'i bka' chems kyi yi ge rnam pa gsum yod par grags pa'i rba bzched dngos dang/ rba bzched la snga dar gyi 'phro 'thud cing/ de la'ang bka' gdams phyogs pa zhig gis kha skong byas pa zhig dang/ bla bzched rnams mthong zhing/ rgyal bzched kyi don blang nas bkod pa'i lo rgyus kyi yig rnying 'ga' re yang mthong ba las/ rgyas bsdus 'phran bu ma gtogs phal cher gtam rgyud ngo bo gcig pa kho nar

*snang la/ mkhas mchog dam pa kun gyis kyang/ de gsum yid ches kyi khungs su mdzad cing/...*⁵

“Therefore the king’s testament is known to have three parts: The real *rBa bzhed* and a *rBa bzhed* with a supplement which continues after the early spread (of Buddhism), written by a *bKa’ gdams pa*; and I have seen the *Bla bzhed*; also have I seen some old historical manuscripts based on the *rGyal bzhed*. Apart from some more or less extensive details, their stories appear to contain exactly the same essence. These three texts are also regarded by all the excellent and holy scholars as three reliable sources.”⁶

The *BZS* should thus be the text with a supplement, written by *bKa’ gdams pa*.

In his article on Tibetan Historiography, H. Hoffmann⁷ puts forward this view:

“As for the *sBa bzhed* ... there are two editions: A ‘Pure *sBa bzhed*’ (*sBa-bzhed gtsang-ma*) and a *sBa-bzhed zhabs-btags-ma* which means ‘With an Annex’.”

If we rely on Sum pa mkhan po’s mention of the *sBa bzhed gtsang ma*,⁸ this text contains material on Glang dar ma and ‘Od srungs. But as we have seen, this is exactly what the *sBa bzhed zhabs btags ma* also has; it

⁵ *sLob dpon chen po padma ’byung gnas kyi rnam par thar pa gsal bar byed pa’i yi ge yid ches gsum ldan zhes bya ba bzhugs soll’ di la slob dpon padma’i rnam thar rgya gar lugs ces bya’ol’* p. 261, 3–5. The same passage has been translated by Blondeau (1980) p. 48.

⁶ We find the clan name *Ba* in several different spellings: *sBa* (*BZC* and *BZS* *passim*), *rBa* (*CBKhG* *passim*), *dPa’* (*CBKhG* p. 77, 4, 7), *sPa* (Sum pa mkhan po p. 155, 26; see note 8) *Bha* (*NRCB* p. 287, 2, 4 and *BCB* p. 887, 2) and ‘Ba’ (*BZS* p. 54, 9) in the texts. Tāranātha (see note 5) continues p. 261, 6: “The different spellings *dBa’ bzhed* and *rBa bzhed* comes [sic] only from the way of pronunciation; they are the same. It is said that there is also the alternative spelling ‘Ba’ *bzhed*, but I have not seen that one; it is (probably) a spelling error for *rBa bzhed*.”

⁷ Hoffmann (1970) p. 176; also quoted by Houston (1980) p. 4.

⁸ Sum pa mkhan po: *dPag bsam ljon bzang*. (Ed.) S. R. Das, Presidency Jail Press, Calcutta 1908, Part II, p. 157: *Glang dar chu lug lo pas sa bdag byas kyang lcags byar bkum/ de rjes de’i sras ’od srung sogs byon zer na sBa bzhed gtsang ma dang mthun par ma zad...*

Referred to by Stein (1961) p.V.

relates the history just after the reign of Khri srong lde btsan until Atiśa. That makes it impossible to sustain the division between *sBa bzhed gtsang ma* and *sBa bzhed zhabs btags ma*, as suggested by Hoffmann. He continues:

“In my opinion, the book (*BZS*) was reworked as late as the period of the Yellow Church, since in an account of the murder of *gLang-dar-ma* by the hermit *Lha-lung dpal-gyi rdo-rje* near the famous *rDo-ring* (obelisk) in front of the *Jo-khang* in Lhasa; there is a mention of a nearby stupa which was erected for the relics of the Fourth Dalai Lama, *Yon-tan rgya-mtsho*.”

This would mean that a revision took place after the death of the Fourth Dalai Lama in 1617. The passage that Hoffmann refers to is found in *BZS* p. 82, 2:

mgon po nag po’ang byung zer nas/ gtsug lag khang dang dga’ ldan bar gyi mchod rten la sku rten byas nas bzhugs pa’i mdun du/...

But for all purposes the same sentence is found in *Klong chen pa’s Chos ’byung* from 1362 in Vol. II, p. 242, 6:

mgon po nag po byon zer nas/ gtsug lag khang dang dga’ ldan gyi bar khang gi mchod rten la sku rten te bzhugs pa’i mdun du/...

So this passage cannot be used to prove that the text was revised after 1617.

On the other hand it is clear that the *BZS* has been revised after *Bu ston* wrote his *Chos ’byung* in 1322, since we find the *BCB* quoted in the *BZS* p. 54, 10:

gSung rab rin po che’i bang mdzod du/ ston mi dang/ rtsen min rgya skad yin pas bod skad du cig bcar ba dang rim gyis pa bya ba yin gsungs/

“In the *gSung rab rin po che’i bang mdzod*⁹ it is said that ‘ston mi’

⁹ The full title is *bDe bar gshegs pa’i bstan pa’i gsal byed chos kyi ’byung gnas gsung rab rin po che’i mdzod*.

and 'rtsen min' are Chinese terms which in Tibetan are called 'cig bcar ba' and 'rim gyis pa'.¹⁰

And in *BCB* p. 890,6 we find:

ton mun dang rtsen mun ni rgya'i skad de gcig car ba dang rim gyis pa zhes pa'ol

BZC

We find no information on the manuscript itself in the 1980 Chinese reprint of the *sBa bzhed*. It is published in the usual way of modern Chinese publications, i.e. typeset in Western softcover book format. A photo shows three pages of the text written in *dbu med*, with 6–7 lines per page in poti format. The introduction gives no hints as to where the manuscript has been obtained, but tells that “obvious misprints in the original have been corrected, but spellings difficult to see or hard to understand have not been changed and are thus found like they were formerly written.” In some cases the redactors have suggested an alternative writing in parentheses. The colophon p. 82, 11–24 is quite informative:

sba gsal snang gi bka' gtsigs kyi yi ge rgyas par bris pa'ol/ bsam yas kyi bka' gtsigs kyi stod bka' chems su bris pa/ bsam yas lta na khyad par du 'di med thabs med gsung ngo/ sba bzhed du grags so/ 'di ni lha sras btsan po'i bka' gtsigs yi ger grags/ sba ni gsal snang bzhed lugs sba bzhed zhes kyang zer/ kha gcig sba ni sang shi'i bzhed lugs yin zhes smra/ don la bsam yas bka' thams (thang) yin zhes 'jig rten grags/ bsam yas bzheng pa'i gtam rgyud 'di las zhib pa med/ 'di rigs mi gcig 'dra min rgyas bsdu' bring gsum las/ 'bring po de la rgyas shos kyi ni 'chan (mchan) btab cing/ bar du bcug byas dpe phyi de la 'di ni bris/ shu bham stus rbdzag stam/ 'di bris dge ba'i rtsa ba yis/ pha mas thog drang nam mkha'i mtha'/ mnyam pa'i sems can thams cad kun/ bde ba can gyi zhing mchog der/ rdzus skyes 'od dpag med pa yil zhal mthong der ni skye bar shog dge'oll lcags yos glang lo hor zla brgyad pa'i yar tshe bzang ba'i nyin/ yi ge pa ni snyas kyi btsun pa ldum bu ma ni arga sidhis bgyis pa lhag chad nam mkha'i padmo bzhin/

¹⁰ See Stein (1969) and Hanson-Barber (1985) for the meaning of the term *cig car*.

“Thus is the extensive version of the edict of *sBa gsal snang* written.

“The first part of the *bSam yas* edict is written as a testament. If you want to see *bSam yas*, it is said that without this text you can not do it. It is called the *sBa bzhed*. This is known as the edict of the king, the son of the Gods. Concerning the ‘sBa’, it is also called *sBa bzhed* because it is the statement of (sBa) *gSal snang*. Some say that the ‘sBa’ (refers to) the statement of (sBa) *Sang shi*. Really people call it the *bSam yas bka' thams (thang)*. There is no more detailed story of the building of *bSam yas* than this. The text has three different versions: the extensive, the abridged and the middling. Of these, the middling has extensive notes added; these have been put between the lines, and I have written this from an original like that.

(Corrupt Sanskrit:) “By the root of virtue of writing this, I wish first of all that my parents and all sentient beings, equal to the sky, are born in a supernatural way in the excellent Buddha field *bDe ba can*, and behold the face of 'Od dpag med! Virtue!

“This text was written by the venerable alms-beggar from *sNyas*, *Ma ni arga sidhi*, on a good day of the first half of the 8th month of the iron-hare-ox (sic!) year. The mistakes are like a lotus in the sky (i.e. there are no mistakes).”

This version of the *sBa bzhed* is different from the one published by Stein (1961), and should be the extensive version according to the colophon. Here mention is also made of three versions, the extensive, the abridged and the middling. As we have already seen, Tāranātha also refers to three different versions, which he calls the *rBa bzhed*, the *Bla bzhed* and the *rGyal bzhed*. These different versions are also remarked upon by Sum pa mkhan po in *dPag bsam ljon bzang*,¹¹ where Sum pa mkhan po says that the three versions called *Bla bzhed*, *rGyal bzhed* and *sPa bzhed* are the same as those called the extensive, the abridged and the middling, and that they all stem from one common root text called the *Mi sPa bzhed*. So it seems that all these authors agree that we can find no more than three versions of the *sBa bzhed*, a fact which is also supported by the *CBKhG*.

¹¹ Quoted by Stein (1961) p.V.

CBKhG

The *Chos byung mkhas pa'i dga' ston* has a unique standing among Tibetan historical texts. It records what is generally accepted to be true copies of original documents from the time of the early kings preserved at bSam yas. This has been shown by G. Tucci, H. Richardson, G. Uray and others.¹² The *sBa bzhed* is extensively quoted too, and the description of the Council of Tibet relies solely on the *sBa bzhed*. dPa' bo gtsug lag mentions his sources in the colophon p. 77,4,7:

... bSam yas kyi dkar chag chen mo'am rgyal rabs dpa' bzhed che 'bring/...

“... the great bSam yas guide or the long and middling dynastic history dPa' bzhed...”

The *CBKhG* contains an almost verbatim reproduction of parts of the *sBa bzhed*, in the version we know as the *BZC*, which is a longer and more extensive version than the *BZS*.

BCB

Bu ston's *Chos 'byung* has for many years been one of our important sources for the early history of Tibet. Even if the author does not mention his sources a close comparison with the *sBa bzhed* will clearly show that he relies solely on this text when dealing with the Council of Tibet. He probably has had access to both editions known to us today. In relating the events of Khri srong lde btsan's reign it looks like he has used the same edition as found in *BZS*, but his narrative is rather abridged so it is difficult to ascertain. But without doubt he has had a copy of the longer edition, the one that we know from the *BZC*, as he quotes information contained only in that edition (see below).

¹² See for example G. Tucci: *The Tombs of the Tibetan Kings*. Serie Orientale Roma I, Is. M.E.O., Roma 1950, H. Richardson: *The First Tibetan Chos-Byung*. *The Tibet Journal* Vol. V, No. 3 (1980) and G. Uray: *The Narrative of Legislation and Organization of the mKhas-pa'i dga'-ston*. *Acta Orientalia Hungarica* Vol. 26,1 (1972), pp. 11–68.

NRCB

One of the most interesting historical texts to surface in recent years is Nyang ral's *Chos 'byung*, also called *Chos 'byung me tog snying po sbrang rtsi'i bcud*. The text was written by Nyang ral pa can Nyi ma 'od zer, either 1124–1192 or 1136–1204.¹³ This makes it the earliest *Chos 'byung* available to us. In this ms. we also find the Council of Tibet extensively described, and once again it is our two versions of the *sBa bzhed* that are the sources, as we shall see below.

The description of the Council of Tibet according to the *sBa bzhed*

In the following I will present the Council of Tibet as it is related in the *sBa bzhed*. As my main text I will use the *BZC*, since that version is the most detailed, and is not a part of another historical text, mixed with editorial comments. The *CBKhG* is used as a reference for the *BZC* as dPa' bo gtsug lag has used this version verbatim, but has interchanged some of the paragraphs.

The description of the Council begins in the *BZS* on p. 53,9 and in the *BZC* on p. 62,13. The *CBKhG* says p. 57,3,2:

mkhan po gshegs pa dang ston rtsen rtsod pa'i tshul ni rba bzhed las/

“Concerning the passing away of the *mkhan po* and the manner of debating of the *ston* and the *rtsen*, (I) quote from the *rBa bzhed*.”

The *BCB* begins with the description of Śāntarakṣita's testament and death on p. 886,6 but does not indicate the source. The *BZS*, the *BZC* and the *CBKhG* bring the information on Śāntarakṣita's testament later in the text (see below). The *NRCB* begins to relate the history of the Council at a later point.

The circumstances leading to the Council of Tibet begin with the death of Śāntarakṣita. He is kicked in the head by a horse¹⁴ or a don-

¹³ For a discussion of Nyang ral's dates, see Meisezahl (1985) p. 9ff. Even if he does not say so in his *Vorbemerkungen*, it seems he prefers the dates 1136–1204 as it is these that are given on the front page. Unfortunately, Meisezahl does not indicate how the ms. came to Berlin, so we do not know where or when it was obtained.

¹⁴ *ita*: *BZC* p. 62,14, *CBKhG* p. 57,2,3 and *BCB* p. 886,7.

key.¹⁵ Ye shes dbang po is appointed leader of the Buddhists.¹⁶ Here, after *BZS* has a short description of the taxation of the Tibetans for the upkeep of the Buddhist community. In the *BZC* (and *CBKhG*) the description of the circumstances leading to the Council of Tibet is much longer. We are first told how Ye shes dbang po consolidates his power: He insists that he is above the Great ministers and that the religious council (*lha chos kyi mdun sa*) is above the state council (*mdun sa chung ngu*); therefore the leader of the Buddhists should be spokesman in the state council. Then the taxation is described. But because of these demands of Ye shes dbang po, Bandhe Nyang ting nge 'dzin and others do not listen to Ye shes dbang po, and many (bad) things happen.¹⁷

Here the *NRCB* p. 286,3,6 begins to relate the Council:

dbang kha dge 'dun la bskur nya (sic!) ting 'dzin bzang po la sogs pa...

In the *BZS* p. 54,1 the following sentence is found:

dbang dge 'dun la bskur nas/ nyang ting nge 'dzin la sogs pa...

but not in the *BZC* or the *CBKhG*, indicating that Nyang ral has used the same version of the *sBa bzhed* as we find in the *BZS*.

Now Nyang ting nge 'dzin and others request Ye shes dbang po to go away to meditate in solitude. *sBa dPal dbyangs* is appointed to fill the vacant seat as leader.¹⁸ At that time a Chinese monk (*hva shang*) called Mahāyāna was staying in Brag dmar. He said:

*lus ngag gi chos bya mi dgos/ lus ngag gi dge bas sangs mi rgyal dran pa med cing yid la byar med pa bsgoms pas sangs rgya*¹⁹

“It will not be necessary to do the *dharma* of body and speech; by do-

¹⁵ *go ru*: *BZS* p. 53,9, *NRCB* does not mention this.

¹⁶ *ring lugs*, see Yamaguchi (1975), especially p. 657, note 13 for the significance of this term.

¹⁷ See Tucci (1958) p. 52 for Nyang ting nge 'dzin, but also Houston (1980) p. 79 n. 9.

¹⁸ In *BZC* p. 64,7, *BZS* p. 54,5 and *CBKhG* p. 57,4,6 *ring lugs*, in *BCB* p. 886,7 *slob dpon* and in *NRCB* p. 287, 1,4 *chos dpon*.

¹⁹ *BZC* p. 64,12. Almost verbatim in *CBKhG* p. 58, 1, 1, *BZS* p. 54,6, *BCB* p. 887,1.

ing pious deeds with the body and speech, Buddhahood will not be reached. By meditating on non-awareness and non-conceptions Buddhahood will be reached.”

We find almost the same sentences, but with more explanations in *NRCB* p. 288,1,6:

lus ngag gi chos spyod dang dge ba byas pas mtho ris thob pa las sangs rgyas mi thob/ bya ba btang ci yang yid la mi byed par byar med/ 'dod 'dun spangs te bdag 'dzin grol nas sangs rgya

“By practising *dharma* with body and speech and having done virtuous actions heaven is reached, but not Buddhahood. Relinquish whatever action and be in non-conceptualization as well as non-action, give up desire and longing; after being saved from the belief in an ‘I’, Buddhahood will be reached.”

Since it is only in the *NRCB* we find these further explanations, it is quite possible that they have been added by Nyang ral.

As a result of these teachings, many of the Tibetans begin to practise Buddhism in the way taught by *hva shang* Mahāyāna. The offerings in *bSam yas* are discontinued; studies and the practice of virtuous actions with body and speech are stopped.²⁰ Only a few still follow the teachings of Śāntarakṣita, among these *sBa ratna*, *Vairocana* and *dPal dbyang*. There is a general agreement that the teachings cannot be reconciled, and a quarrel and a fight commence. Some of the adherents of *hva shang* Mahāyāna hurt themselves, others threaten the followers of Śāntarakṣita. When the king hears this, he dispairs and orders that Ye shes dbang po shall be summoned. When he arrives at the castle the king explains the problems.

At this point Ye shes dbang po refers to Śāntarakṣita's testament:

mkhan po 'da' khar 'di skad gsungs tel/ yong ni sangs rgyas kyi bstan

²⁰ This might have been one of the very important factors in the king's decision to ask Kamalaśīla to come to Tibet to vanquish the teachings of Mahāyāna. What the king needed was a strong clergy as a countermeasure to the nobility supported by *bon*. This seemed to be crumbling with the increasing popularity of Mahāyāna's teachings. For a view of the politico-economic relationships in this period, see Beckwith (1977) and Wylie (1980).

pa gar byung bar mu stegs kyi rgol ba'i dgra re 'gran du 'ong ba yang 'byung rgyu yin na/ bod yul du bstan pa lnga brgya'i tha ma la byung pas/ mu stegs kyi rgol ba ni mi 'byung/ sangs rgyas pa nyid lta ba ma mthun te risod par 'gyur gyis/ de lta bu byung na' nga'i slob ma ka ma la shi la bya ba cig bal yul na 'dug pa spyan drong la/ de dang shags 'gyer du chug la/ rgyal pos brdums gyis shig rtsod pa chos phyogs su 'dum par 'gyur rol zhes mkhan po 'da' khar gsungs!²¹

“When the *mkhan po* was dying, he said: ‘In the future, wherever the doctrine of the Buddha arises, each time it will come to a fight with hostile heretics. But the way it will come about in Tibet in the last five hundred year cycle of the Buddhist teachings will not be as a fight with the heretics; it will be a dispute among Buddhists with disagreeing views. Therefore, when this happens, invite a disciple of mine called Kamalaśīla, who is staying in Nepal. He will enter the dispute with the king as conciliator. The dispute will then be solved in accordance with the *dharma*.’ So said the dying *mkhan po*.”

Thus admonished, the king sends envoys to Nepal to invite Kamalaśīla. Meanwhile, the master of the *ston min* (i.e. Mahāyāna) with three hundred servants, goes into seclusion in bSam gtan gling (in the bSam yas monastery) where he studies the *Shes rab 'bum* (*Śatasāhasrikā-prajñāpāramitā*) for four months.²² But he rolls up the *dGongs pa nges par 'grel pa* (*Samdhinirmocanasūtra*) with the sole of his foot saying: “This is not *dharma*” and then he throws it away.²³

²¹ BZC p. 66,6; referred almost verbatim in CBKhG p. 58,2,5. Described a bit differently in the BZS p. 56,1 and in the NRCB p. 288,3,5. The latter two are identical but for one interesting detail: Where the BZS reads

...*bod yul du lnga brgya'i tha mar gyur pas sangs rgyas kyi chos dar kyang mu tegs kyi rgol ba ni mi 'ong nal...*

we find in the NRCB *sangs rgyas* exchanged with *slob dpon padma 'byung gnas kyis bstan ma bcu gnyis la gnyer gtad pas*, “because Padma Saṃbhava made the twelve *bsTan ma* caretakers”. This sentence is taken by Nyang ral from the second version of the Council (see below). It is found in the BZC p. 72,22.

²² The *Śatasāhasrikā-prajñāpāramitā* is one of the sūtras often quoted by Mahāyāna and his followers. See Faber (1985) p. 53 note 22. In BZS p. 56,7 and NRCB p. 289,1,5 is the text designated *Yum rgyas pa*.

²³ See Wayman (1977) pp. 141–3 and Wayman (1978) pp. 44–58 for a discussion of Mahāyāna’s rejection of the *Samdhinirmocanasūtra*.

While the king is waiting for Kamalaśīla, he has Ye shes dbang po explain to him the difference in the views held by Mahāyāna and Śāntarakṣita; and when he understood them he said many times: “Ye shes dbang po is my teacher!” and paid homage to him.

Now Kamalaśīla arrives in Tibet. The first meeting between him and Mahāyāna takes place by the river. Kamalaśīla is on one bank, Mahāyāna with his retinue on the other. Kamalaśīla wants to test Mahāyāna’s understanding, and revolves his stick three times over his head, which means ‘What makes the three worlds go round?’ Mahāyāna shakes the folds of his cloak two times answering ‘It is caused by belief in subject–object’.²⁴ Mahāyāna then says: “He is one to fear.”

Everything is now made ready for the disputation. In Byang chub gling (in bSam yas) lion thrones are erected. The king sits in the middle; Mahāyāna on the left on a lion throne with his retinue behind him, and there are many followers. Kamalaśīla is on the right lion throne, with only a few followers. The king gives the two contenders each a garland of white flowers, and gives a short review of the events leading up to the dispute, and ends: The loser gives the garland to the other with no pride, according to the way of the *dharma*. Then Mahāyāna asks if he shall start asking or answering. Kamalaśīla answers that Mahāyāna shall begin by explaining his own way of thinking:

Hva shang na re/ thams cad sems kyi rnam par rtog pas bskyed pas/ dge mi dge'i dbang gis las dge mi dges mtho ris dang ngan song gi 'bras bu myong zhing 'khor ba na 'khor rol gang zhig ci la yang mi sems zhing/ ci yang yid la mi byed pa de 'khor ba las yongs su thar bar 'gyur rol/ de lta bas na ci la yang mi bsam mol/ sbyin pa la sogs pa'i chos spyod rnam bcu spyod pa ni skye bo dge ba'i 'phro med pa/ blo zhan pa/ dbang po btul po rnam la bstan pa yin/ sngon blo sbyang pa dbang po rnon po dag la sprin dkar nag gnyis gang gis kyang nyi ma sgrib pa ltar/ dge sdig gnyis kas kyang sgrib pas/ de bas na ci la yang mi sems/ ci la yang mi rtog/ ci yang mi spyod pa ni mi dmigs pa gcig char 'jug pas sa bcu pa dang 'dra'ol ces gsungs pa²⁵

²⁴ These explanations are given as notes in BZS p. 56, 14–16.

²⁵ BZC p. 68,11 and almost verbatim CBKhG p. 58,4,7, BZS p. 57,16. Also NRCB p. 289,3,3 has this almost verbatim, together with a few sentences from the alternative version found in the BZC (see below), and Nyang ral has also added several sentences to facilitate understanding. In BCB p. 888,2 we find an abridged version.

“*Hva shang* said: ‘Because everything is created by the dichotomic mind, then the power of virtue and non-virtue leads to virtuous and non-virtuous *karma* and we experience the results of heaven and hell and going round in *saṃsāra*. Whoever does not think at all, does not conceptualize at all, he will become completely liberated from *saṃsāra*. Therefore, do not think at all. The practice of generosity, etc., and the practice of the ten religious practices are teachings for people with little virtue, weak intellect and dull senses. For those who have purified their minds earlier, and have sharp senses, it is like the sun that is obscured by clouds, no matter if they are black or white. Therefore, since both virtue and sin are obscuring, do not think at all, do not reflect at all, do not practise at all. But entering instantaneously without an objective referent is like the tenth *bhūmi*.’ So he said.”

Now this is in complete concord with the teachings from *hva shang* Mahāyāna as we know them from other sources.²⁶

In his article on the Sanskrit ms. of the third *Bhāvanākrama*, Obermiller shows that the *BCB*

“... represents a literal reproduction of the text of the *Bhāvanākrama* which is only slightly condensed. It is thus quite clear that Bu ston has used the *Bhāvanākrama* as a source ...”

“... in communicating a most important event in the history of Tibetan Buddhism, he (Bu ston) bases his account upon a source, the title of which is nowhere mentioned by him, and which now discloses itself as the work of Kamalaśīla, the principal personage connected with the said event.”²⁷

But as we know now, Bu ston does not quote the *Bhāvanākrama*; he quotes the *sBa bzhed*. It is the *sBa bzhed* that quotes the *Bhāvanākrama*, and even Mahāyāna’s statement just referred to above is taken from Kamalaśīla’s third *Bhāvanākrama*:

Gang zhig sems kyi rnam par rtog pas bskyed pa’i dge ba dang mi dge ba’i las kyi dbang gis sems can rnam mtho ris la sogs pa’i ’bras bu

²⁶ For a comprehensive description of Mahāyāna’s teachings, see Gomez (1983b). In his article Gomez collects all the material known to us ascribed to Mahāyāna.

²⁷ Obermiller (1935) p. 10–11.

*myong zhing ’khor ba na ’khor roll gang dag ci yang mi sems ci yang mi byed pa de dag ni ’khor ba las yongs su thar par ’gyur roll de lta ba na ci yang mi bsam moll sbyin pa la sogs pa dge ba spyad par yang mi bya’oll sbyin pa la sogs pa spyod pa ni skye bo blun po’i dbang du mdzad nas bstan pa kho na yin no*²⁸

Of course, we cannot know for certain if Mahāyāna’s explanations have been faithfully recorded verbatim *both* by the reputed author of the *sBa bzhed*, *sBa gsal snang*, and Kamalaśīla to ensure the similarity of the passage, but this hardly seems convincing. As we have got the Sanskrit original of the third *Bhāvanākrama*, it would appear that this really has been written by Kamalaśīla, while the *sBa bzhed* was written later, since it relates the death of Kamalaśīla. Thus it must be considered that the third *Bhāvanākrama*’s interpretation of Mahāyāna’s statements has been copied by the *sBa bzhed*. This is also supported by the rest of the text concerning the Council. As we can see, most of the contributions to the debate are found to be almost identical in both the third *Bhāvanākrama* and the *sBa bzhed*.

This is the only defence ascribed to Mahāyāna in the *sBa bzhed*; now Kamalaśīla takes over. His argumentation for his own views is rather well-known,²⁹ so I will not quote it here.

Then the king admonishes the attendants of Mahāyāna and Kamalaśīla to join the dispute. But in the *sBa bzhed* we find only two more contributions by followers of Kamalaśīla; further contributions by followers of Mahāyāna are not included.

dPal dbyangs speaks first. He argues that it is not possible to reject the six *pāramitās*; if one does, it is not possible to reach Buddhahood.³⁰

²⁸ *sGom pa’i rim pa tha ma*, TTP No. 5312, Vol. 102 p. 38,5,7–39,1,1. For a translation of this passage, see Lamotte’s translation of the third *Bhāvanākrama* in Demiéville (1952) p. 348.

²⁹ See Gomez (1983a) for a treatment of the *Bhāvanākramas* and the Council of Tibet. The concordance between Kamalaśīla’s remarks in the *sBa bzhed* and the third *Bhāvanākrama* are: The *BZC* pp. 68,21–70,7, the *BZS* pp. 58,8–59,13 and *CBKhG* pp. 59,1,3–59,2,5 contain abridged passages from the *Bhāvanākrama* pp. 39,1,2–39,4,2, in most cases verbatim. The *NRCB* pp. 290, 3,6–291,3,3 also contains the same material, but as we have seen before, Nyang ral adds some comments of his own throughout the passage. Bu ston pp. 888,4–889,4 gives a condensed version.

³⁰ The *BZC* p. 70,9–20, the *CBKhG* pp. 59,2,6–3,2, the *BCB* p. 889,4–7, *NRCB* pp. 291,3,4–292,3,4. In the *BZS* pp. 59,15–60,7 the same passage is ascribed to Sang shi. For the problems concerned with the identification of Sang shi and dPal dbyangs, see Tucci (1958) p. 11ff and Yamaguchi (1975).

Now Ye shes dbang po continues. He gives the arguments that the subsequent generations of Tibetan scholars also use when attacking Mahāyāna's views:

“It is necessary to examine both the so-called instantaneous approach and the so-called gradual approach. If you enter gradually, there is no reason for disputation: you are like us. If you enter instantaneously, why do anything now? What is faulty (in the thought of) being in the state of Buddhahood from the beginning? Because also in ascending a mountain it is necessary to do it step by step; you cannot go there in one step. Likewise, as it is very difficult to reach the first *bhūmi*, how much more so to obtain omniscience. If you have not done anything to attain Buddhahood, you need the basic teachings. The *ston* and the *rtsen* are not alike. We *brtse min* (sic!) study all the scriptures and rely on the three discriminative insights (*shes rab*) of hearing, thinking and meditating, then we know that our understanding (*don*) is not mistaken. We study the ten religious practises. By meditation we obtain patience in the first *bhūmi* and we also enter the perfect faultlessness. Then during the nine *bhūmis* we become gradually purified by discriminative insight and learn the ten *pāramitās*. After the mind-stream has been purified and the two accumulations have been completed, Buddhahood is found. But if one, like you, does not collect the two accumulations, does not purify the mind so that you do not even know how to perform worldly actions, how can you obtain omniscience and approach knowledge and all that should be known? What is the cause for the accomplishment of Buddhahood, the excellent benefit for oneself and others? It is the fulfilment of the two accumulations. If there is no benefit by Voidness alone, even to oneself, how can you be of benefit to others? As you continuously depend on food, drink and clothing just to maintain your life, if you do not adhere to them you die. If you don't taste food for seven days you starve and then die. Therefore it is so very necessary to do the ten religious practices. So you do not have these basic (teachings); and to honor Buddha with a *dharma* which divides means from discriminative insight is a deceit.

“The *Bodddhisattva* creates *bodhicitta* for the benefit of beings, then he applies himself to benefit others, and then he has built up the accumulation of merit. He studies skillfully all the objects of knowledge and purifies his mind in relation to the three discriminative in-

sights; (then) he has built up the accumulation of highest wisdom (*ye shes*). After having purified the two obscurations, he has removed all defilements of the mind and (obtains) perfect powers and Buddhahood. Then he appears spontaneously to work for the benefit of all sentient beings to establish them in the state of Buddhahood as long as *samsāra* is not empty. So it is said in many scriptures.

“Whoever does not think is like an egg. If you walk without consciousness, you will also stagger about. Then how can you understand the *dharma*?³¹ Therefore you must read the *sūtrantas* to reach enlightenment. You must contemplate calming the mind (*zhi gnas*) and intellectual insight (*lhag mthong*) in solitude, and the mind will understand a dawning experience. Therefore you shall collect the (two) accumulations. If you ask how that mind is: Understand that the relative mind is like a mirage, and the absolute is unborn. If you genuinely understand that the whole of existence (*chos thams cad*) is like the inner part of a banana plant (i.e. hollow), the three times will not become an object for you. Because you know that things (*chos*) and beings do not have an ‘I’ there is no indolence, no overactivity. One after the other (*zhi gnas* and *lhag mthong*) will be joined with the nature (of mind). Meditation is like that.”

The *ston min* can't answer this and accepts defeat. We read in the *BZC* p. 72, 11:

me tog gtor nas 'pham par khas blangs so/ yang lugs gcig la

“After having strewn flowers, they accepted defeat. According to another version:”

And then comes another (and shorter) version of the Council. This is not found in the *BZS*; but we find condensed parts of this version in the *CBKhG* on p. 60, 3, 5, where it is put after the description of Kamalāśīla's *Bhāvanākramas*:

rba bzhed la lar sngar gyi me tog gtor nas pham par khas blangs so zhes pa'i 'og tu yang lugs gcig la

³¹ Here we find the following sentence inserted in *CBKhG* p. 59, 4, 4 and *BCB* p. 890, 3: “By staying in a sleeping state where you do nothing at all, you don't even taste food but starve and die. How can you then accomplish Buddhahood?”

“In some versions of the *rBa bzhed*, after the aforementioned (sentence) ‘After having strewn flowers, they accepted defeat,’ we find: ‘According to another version:’”

It is not clear what is meant by “According to another version”. Houston (1980) p. 42 translates the above passage from the *CBKhG* thus:

“In some (version of) the *Rba bzhed*, after the (*Cig char ba*) had strewn flowers as before (mentioned), they acknowledged defeat. In some later version (*lugs*),...”

Obviously, Houston interprets the passage to mean that in different versions of the *sBa bzhed* we find different descriptions of the Council. But this is not the case as can be seen from the fact that we find the two descriptions of the Council in the same version of the *sBa bzhed*, viz. the *BZC*. To me it is much more plausible to interpret this passage to mean that there are several, or at least two differing descriptions of the Council known to the author or redactor of the extensive version of the *sBa bzhed*, and after presenting one, he gives the other. I am inclined to believe that it is the author of the *sBa bzhed* who has written the two versions, since it is clear from the contents of the second version that it is rather old, as it uses some very archaic words. If this is the case, then the description of the Council is not contemporary, but of a later date when several versions already had come into being. On the other hand, if it is an addition made by a later redactor, it must have been done before Nyang ral wrote his *Chos 'byung*, since it contains material from both versions.

The *BZC* continues with the other version:

rgya nag gi dge stong byung nas/ kho na re/ tshig la snying po med/ tha snyad kyi chos kyi 'tshang mi rgya/ sems rtogs na dkar po chig thub yin pas des chog zer nas/ de'i chos lugs kyi bstan bcos bsam gtan nyal ba'i 'khor lo/ bsam gtan gyi lon/ yang lon/ lta ba'i rgyab sha/ mdo sde brgya (sic!) bcu khungs zhes bya ba'i bstan bcos lnga brisams nas/ rgya nag gi chos lugs dkar po chig thub 'di bod kham thams cad du 'phel lo/

“A Chinese monk appeared and said: ‘Words have no essence. You will not reach Buddhahood by religious terminology. If you under-

stand the mind, since that is ‘the one key to realization’³² it is thereby sufficient.’

“Therefore he composed these five works that are in accord with his religious system:

bSam gtan nyal ba'i 'khor lo

bSam gtan gyi lon

Yang lon

lTa ba'i rgyab sha

mDo sde brgya (brgyad) bcu khungs

This Chinese religious system, ‘the one key to realization’, spread all over Tibet.”

The list of texts written by the Chinese is not included in the *CBKhG*. In the *BCB*³³ p. 887,5, after the passage where the king has sent messengers for Kamalaśīla, we find the same five texts mentioned, and likewise in the *NRCB* p. 287,1,4, just in the beginning of the description of the Council together with Nyang rals own comments:

rgya nag gi mkhan po ma ha ya na'i slob bu sgom phrug pa rnam dar tel 'khor bar skye ba'i rgyu rang ngo rang gi ma shes pas lan rang ngo shes nas rtogs na sangs rgya de'i phyir sems ngo 'phrod dgos de ngo shes na dkar po chig thub yin 'di'i gzhung 'dzugs pa la sems lon bsu (sic!) bya ba'i bstan bcos su mdzad do sems ngo 'phrod na nyal bas chog pas/ bsam gtan nyal 'dug gi 'khor lo dang/ de'i gnad ston pa'i bsam gtan gyi 'khor lo dang/ de'i gags sel ba la bsam gtan gyi yang lon no de'i gdams pa rigs pas bsgrub pa la man ngag lta ba'i rgyab sha

³² *dkar po chig thub* is one of the very old designations used for the *cig car* system of thought. Literally it means “to be able (to obtain realization using just) one way”, that way of course being the recognition of one’s own mind. To that is added “the white”, meaning, as we also see it in other old texts, that it is the best. I will here use the “translation” “the one key to realization”. We find the term used only in this version of the Council.

³³ Especially the last text, *mDo sde brgyad bcu khungs* has been treated by Kimura (1981), who suggests on p. 187 that it is a translation of the Chinese treatise *Zhujing yaochao*. He continues: “Si Bu-ston attribue cet ouvrage a Hva-shang Mahāyāna, c’est probablement parce qu’il était un des principaux textes que ce maître chinois a apportés au Tibet et sur lesquels il se serait fondé pour diffuser le Dhyāna chinois.” But as we have seen the texts are not ascribed to Mahāyāna directly; this might be Bu ston himself who has done that.

dang/ de'i lung gis sgrub pa la mdo sde brgyad bcu khungs zhes pa mdzad/

“The disciples of the Chinese *mkhan po* Mahāyāna propagated. They said that the reason for rebirth in *samsāra* is not to recognize one's own mind; after having recognized one's own mind, if you realize that, you will reach Buddhahood. Therefore it is necessary to identify the mind. If it is recognized, that is ‘the one key to realization’. As authoritative treatises the works called ‘The Treatises on the Mind’ were written. Because it is sufficient to sleep if you have identified the mind, the *bSam gtan nyal 'dug gi 'khor lo* was written. To show its essence, the *bSam gtan gyi 'khor lo* was written; to show its dissipation of obstructions the *bSam gtan gyi yang lon* was written; its instructions based on logic proof were written in the *Man ngag lta ba'i rgyab sha* and its proofs based on the scriptures were written in the *mDo sde brgyad bcu khungs*.”

As can be seen, there is a slight difference between the names of the texts given in the *BZC* and the *NRCB*.

The *BZC* and the *NRCB* are not the only texts that record the names of the texts written by the Chinese. In Sa skyā paṇḍita's *sKye bu dam pa rnams la springs pa'i yi ge*³⁴ p. 331.4.6 we find almost verbatim the above quoted passage from the *NRCB*, including Nyang ral's comments, thus making it clear that Sa skyā paṇḍita has copied this passage from the *NRCB*.

To return to the second version of the Council found in the *BZC*, this gives the same basic information on the events leading to the Council as we have already met with. After the preliminaries, the dispute itself begins thus in *BZC* p. 73,21:

der slob dpon ka ma la si las rgya nag gi chos lugs ji ltar yin zhes phyogs snga dris pa nal rgya nag na re/ kyed kyi chos lugs skyabs 'gro sems bskyed nas bzung spre'u shing la 'dzegs pa ltar mas 'dzeg yin/ nged kyi chos lugs 'di bya byed kyi chos kyis 'tshang mi rgya bas rnam par mi rtog pa bsgoms nas sems rtogs pa nyid kyis sangs rgyas te khyung nam mkha' las shing rtser 'bab pa ltar yas 'bab kyi chos yin

³⁴ *skye bu dam pa rnams la springs pa'i yi ge*. The Complete Works of the Great Masters of the Sa skyā pa Sect of Tibetan Buddhism Vol. 5. The Complete works of Paṇḍita Kun-dga' rgyal-mtshan. Tokyo 1968, pp. 330, 4.6–333.4.2.

pas dkar po chig thub yin no/ zhes zer ro/ de la slob dpon gyis/ khyed kyi dpe don gnyis ka mi 'thad pa las/ khyung nam mkha' las glo bur du 'dab gshog rdzogs par skyes nas shing rtser 'bab ba'am/ 'on te brag la sogs par skyes nas rim gyis 'dab gshog rdzogs par byas te 'bab/ dang po ni mi srid lal/ gnyis pa ni rim gyis pa'i dper rung gis/ cig char ba'i dper mi rung ngo gsungs/ de nas rgya nag mkhan pos dpe la lan ma thebs pa dang/ der slob dpon gyis/ khyed kyi dpe nor bar ma zad/ don yang 'khrul tel/ rnam par mi rtog pa'i sgom de cil/ rnam par rtog pa phyogs gcig bkag pa tsam yin nam/ rnam par rtog pa mtha' dag bkag dgos/ dang po ltar phyogs gcig bkag pa yin no zhe nal/ de ltar na gnyid dang rgyal (brgyal) ba la sogs pa yang rnam par mi rtog par thall/ rtog pa phyogs gcig bkag pa yod pa'i phyir ro/ rtog pa mtha' dag bkag pa yin no zhe nal/ de ltar la khyed mi rtog pa sgom pa'i tshel/ mi rtog pa sgom snyam pa'i rtog pa sngon du btang dgos sam mi dgos/ mi dgos na khams gsum gyi sems can thams cad la yang sgom skye bar thall/ sgom snyam pa'i rtog pa sngon du ma btang yang sgom skye ba'i phyir ro/ mi rtog pa sgom snyam pa'i rtog pa sngon du btang dgos nal/ de nyid rtog pa yin pas mi rtog pa sgom pa'i dam bca' nyams tel/ dper na nga smra bcad byas pa yin zhes brjod na smra bcad shor ba'am/ ca co ma byed ca cor 'gro ba bzhin no/ zhes bya ba la sogs pa lung dang rig pas sun phyung ba na rgya nag mkhan po spobs pa med par gyur to/ der rgyal pos bka' bstsal pa/ lan yod na gsungs shig mkham pos smras pa/ mgor thog brgyab pa dang mtshung par lan mi shes so/ rgyal pos bka' bstsal pa/ de lta na slob dpon la me tog gi phreng ba phul la bzod par gsol to/ dkar po chig thub kyi chos lugs bor la lung rigs dang mi 'gal ba rgya gar gyi chos lugs bzhin du gyis shig slan chad rgya nag gi chos lugs dkar po chig thub 'di byed pa byung na chad pa bcad do zhes bod khams kun tu khrims bcas te rgya nag gi dpe rnams bsdu nas bsam yas su gter du sbas so/ der rgya nag mkhan po yi mug te rang gi gnas su song ngo/ chos grva der lham lus pas/ ltas de las spags (dpags) na sangs rgyas kyi bstan pa 'jigs ('jig) khar nga'i bstan pa yang lham tsam cig lus par 'gyur ro/ zhes 'khor rnams la lung bstan to zhes brag go/ phyis dge ba'i bshes gnyen mkhas pa rnams na re/ rgya nag mkhan pos chos mi shes kyang ltas cung zad shes pa zhid stel/ ding sang chos khung ma rnams bor nas sems ngo 'phrod pas sangs rgya bar 'dod pa dkar po chig thub du 'gro ba'i rgyu mtshan de yin gsung/

“Then *ācārya* Kamalaśīla asked the opponent: ‘How is the Chinese religious system?’ The Chinese said: ‘In your religious system you

start to take refuge and create *bodhicitta*. It is like a monkey climbing up a tree. In our religious system you do not reach Buddhahood by religious actions, but after meditation on non-dichotomy; by that understanding of the mind you reach Buddhahood. Our religion is like a Garuda swooping down from the sky to the top of a tree, and that is 'the one key to realization'.³⁵

"The *ācārya* then said: 'Neither of your similes are acceptable: For a Garuda to swoop suddenly from the sky to the top of a tree, either it must be born with perfect wings, or if it is born on the ground it gradually completes its wings and then swoops down. Because the first alternative does not exist and the second is a simile fitting for the gradualist, the simile of the one who adheres to the instantaneous realization is not a proper one.'

"To that simile the Chinese *mkhan po* could not give a suitable answer. Then the *ācārya* said: 'Not only is your simile wrong, your idea is also mistaken. What is non-dichotomic meditation? Should just one part of dichotomy be obstructed, or is it necessary to obstruct all dichotomy? If you say like the first, that just one part is to be obstructed, then sleep and fainting and so on also become non-dichotomy, because part of the dichotomy is obstructed. If you say that all dichotomy shall be obstructed, then at the time when you meditate on non-dichotomy, do you or do you not need to think in advance about meditating on non-dichotomy? If you do not need to be conscious of meditation to obtain non-dichotomy, all the beings of the three spheres can reach it without effort, therefore meditation (on non-dichotomy) is born. If you need to think in advance about meditation on non-dichotomy, then *that* is dichotomy and therefore you have spoiled the statement of meditation on non-dichotomy. For example if I say: "I am not talking" then I am breaking the non-talking. Or it is like (saying) "Don't make noise", (then that) has become noise.' This and other things did he say.

"When the Chinese *mkhan po* was defeated (thus) by textual references and logic, he dared not venture any more. Then the king said: 'If you have an answer, speak up!' The *mkhan po* said: 'It is as if I have been struck in the head by lightning, so I do not know an answer.' The king said: 'Then give the garland to the *ācārya* and ask

³⁵ The *NRCB* p. 290, 3,1-2 mixes parts of this passage with the general description of Mahāyāna's teachings taken from the third *Bhāvanākrama*.

forgiveness. The religious system of "the one key to realization" is to be given up; accordingly the Indian religious system which is not in disagreement with the scriptures and logic should be practiced. Henceforth, if somebody appears who is practicing the Chinese religious system "the one key to realization", he will be punished.' So was the law made all over Tibet; the Chinese books were collected and then hidden in bSam yas as 'treasures'. Then the Chinese *mkhan po* was dejected; he went back to his own place.

"It is said that when he left a shoe in the college, he prophesied to his followers: 'If you want to interpret that omen, when the Buddha's teachings are about to be destroyed, my teaching will be left, like my shoe.'

"Later learned *kalyānamitras* have said: 'The Chinese *mkhan po* did not know the *dharma*, but he knew a bit of augury.' This can be said (to be true) because nowadays the reliable *dharma* has been thrown away by some, and they go for 'the one key to realization', believing they will reach Buddhahood by recognizing the mind."

This description of the Council is not to be found in the third *Bhāvanākrama*, and constitutes thus a truly different version, even if the contents are similar. It is clear that some of the last part of the above quoted passage is a later added note. From "Later learned *kalyānamitras* have said..." it is obvious, but I would suggest that the note already begins by "It is said that because he left a shoe in the college..." because the story of the shoe that was left is a repetition of an earlier event when a Chinese monk was expelled from Tibet by the ministers in opposition to Buddhism during the minority of King Khri srong lde btsan. That event is described in both our editions of the *sBa bzhed*, in the *BZC* on p. 9,6-9 and in the *BZS* on p. 8,5-7. This added note clearly attacks the rNying ma ideas concerning the recognition of mind like we find it in *rDzogs chen*. These attacks were initiated by lHa bla ma Zhi ba 'od (11th cent.) who was an ardent follower of Atiśa, and the note might well be written by a follower of his.³⁶ This is supported by the statement by Tāranātha, as we have seen above, that points to a bka' gdams pa as the author of the *Zhabs brtags ma*.

In the alternative version we also find the interesting information that Chinese books were hidden as "treasures" (*gter*), a statement we

³⁶ See Karmay (1979) and Karmay (1980).

find quoted in both the *BCB* p. 890.5 and in the *NRCB* p. 293,3,3. Whether the texts have survived in this way or not it is quite evident that the views represented by Chinese monks did not disappear from Tibet, as can be seen from the survival of extracts of the Chinese texts in later Tibetan texts.³⁷

After giving this alternative version of the Council, the *BZC* now goes on with the first version on p. 75,17. The Chinese fraction has been defeated; and now the king gives his verdict.³⁸ He says that the Chinese *dharma* called *ston min* or *cig char* is faulty and should be brought to an end. Strangely enough the *BZC* does not contain the very famous statement that in the future it is Nāgārjuna's system that must be followed. But we find that one in all the other editions, here quoted from the *CBKhG* p. 60.1.2:

*gzhan khyed kyi 'khor rnams dang bod rnams da slan chad lta ba na
ga rdzu na'i lugs zung/ spyod pa pha rol du phyin pa drug la gyis la
chos spyod nam pa bcu nyam su long/ sgom pa shes rab nam pa
gsum la blo sbyongs la thabs dang shes rab zung du chud cing 'grel ba
zhi gnas dang lthag mihong la sgoms cig/*

“Furthermore, from now on your followers and the Tibetans shall practice Nāgārjuna's view, which is the union of the practice of the six *pāramitās* together with the ten religious practices, and study meditation on the three discriminative insights. You shall unite means and discriminative insight, which is connected to meditation on calming the mind and intellectual insight.”

After stressing these points further, it is said by the king *BZC* p. 75,23:

*chos ni rtogs pa dka' zhing zab par gyur pas/ rgya gar gyi mkhas pa
rab tu byung bar grags³⁹ pa rgyal pos spyan drang te yon bdag byas/ lo
tsatsha ba mkhas pas gtan la phab pa'i chos de la 'jug par bya'o/ rgyal
pos yon bdag ma byas/ lo tsatsha ba mkhas pas gtan la ma phab pa'i
chos de la 'jug par mi bya'o/*

³⁷ See for example Faber (1985) pp. 48–50.

³⁸ This corresponds to the *BZS* p. 62,3, the *CBKhG* p. 59,4,7, the *BCB* p. 890.5 and the *NRCB* p. 294,2,1.

³⁹ In the *BZS* p. 62,11 we read *rab tu grags pa*, likewise in the *CBKhG* p. 60,1,4 *rab tu gyur par grags*, and I have translated accordingly.

“Because the *dharma* is deep and thus difficult to understand, the king has invited well-known learned Indians, and acted as a sponsor. That *dharma*, which the wise translators have revised, should be entered. That *dharma*, which the king has not sponsored, and which has not been revised by the learned translators, should not be entered.”

Three copies of this edict are made and distributed. Then *hva shang* Mahāyāna builds a temple and returns to China.

Conclusions

As we have seen it is told in the Tibetan historical literature that three different editions of the *sBa bzhed* were written. Two of these we have today, known here as the *BZC* and the *BZS*. But it is also evident that versions other than these have not been available to Tibetan historians since the time of Nyang ral, since we do not find any further information given by these authors than what is included in the *sBa bzhed*. Thus it is also clear that the *sBa bzhed* has been the only source for these writers, as it is for us today, concerning the Council of Tibet and the details of the reign of King Khri srong lde btsan.

Since the first edition of the *sBa bzhed* became known in 1961, the reliability of the text and the problem of later editions have been major obstacles for Tibetologists in its evaluation. As I have shown here, at least when we work with the Council of Tibet, the text has been edited surprisingly little, for we find the same material almost verbatim in all the versions used.

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